

Insect resistance

Mass rearing of the rice leaf folder

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A method for mass rearing of the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* has been developed at IRRI. It consists of the following steps (see figure):

1. In a greenhouse, larvae are reared on rice plants growing in earthenware pots 30 cm in diameter. Each pot is covered with a mesh sleeve supported by a wire frame. Access into the sleeve is through a side sleeve.
2. Newly emerged adults are transferred from the sleeves to cylindrical plastic oviposition cages (27 cm in diameter and 65 cm tall) fitted with sleeves. Each cage has a pot of rice plants and a feeder containing cotton batting saturated with a solution of honey in water (25% by volume). We designed two types of oviposition cages. One with few mesh openings for air circulation is for use in the dry, airconditioned laboratory. The other with extensive mesh areas is for the humid, screened insectary.
3. Eggs are collected from the oviposition plants daily for the first 7 days (when 85% of the eggs are laid) and are placed in petri dishes on wet filter paper.
4. Newly hatched larvae are transferred daily with a fine-pointed, wet camel's hair brush from the petri dishes to the sleeved potted plants.

An average of about 120 eggs/female initially put into the oviposition cages is obtained. The egg hatching rate was 91.7%; the eggs hatched in the morning of the 4th day at a mean temperature of about 23°C. Survival from the first instar to the adult ranged from 78.6% to 97.3%, averaging 87.0%.

Procedure for rearing rice leaf folders and the relationship to varietal screening.

The yield of insects from a culture that can be maintained with 84 working hours in a 7-day week has been calculated.

If 15 sleeves with larvae are set up each week, 60 sleeves will always be on hand. Each sleeve will accommodate 50 larvae. With an average of 87% survival about 650 adults/week will be produced — more than enough to set up 15 oviposition cages with about 25 adults/cage. If the cages average 11 females each, more than 16,000 eggs/week should be produced. With a hatching rate of about 92%, about 15,000 first-instar larvae/week should be

available. About 7% of them are needed to continue the culture; 93% can be used to screen varieties for resistance. Thus it may be possible to screen 400 varieties/week in the greenhouse by artificial infestation with first-instar larvae, using 3 pots, each with 5 plants of each variety and 2 first-instar larvae/plant. Infested plants are allowed to remain in the greenhouse until the larvae are in the 5th and 6th instar, about 16 days. Then the varieties are scored by determining the percentage of folded leaves and the number of surviving larvae. ■